

STANDARD TESTS FOR THE TOUGHNESS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES - SOME BONES OF CONTENTION

by JG Williams*, P Davies** and A J Brunner***

* Department of Mechanical Engineering, Imperial College, London, UK

** Marine Materials Lab, IFREMER, Centre de Brest, Plouzane, France

*** Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Testing & Research, EMPA, Dübendorf, Switzerland

ABSTRACT

A description is given of problems which arise in developing a Mode I fracture toughness test for composite laminates. The definition of initiation is considered and it is concluded that visual and non-linearity detection methods are inherently unreliable. An arbitrary method based on a 5% compliance change is advocated. The nature of the initial defect is also discussed and problems arising with molded in cracks are noted. It is suggested that some form of precracking is necessary. It is also suggested that the full resistance or 'R' crack for the composite is a preferable method for characterising composite toughness. Similar problems in Mode II tests are also described.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates are ideal candidates for modelling with fracture mechanics. For high modulus fibres the deformations are elastic and delaminations are close approximations to sharp cracks. It is therefore not surprising that the delamination toughness of such laminates has been characterised using linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM). Rather unusually the methods have almost all used the energy release rate G and associated resistance or 'R' curves. In the USA, at least, the tendency for most cases where LEFM is used is to use stress intensity factors (K) but since, for isotropic materials, $K^2 = EG$, the equivalence is tacitly assumed. In composite laminates the plies surrounding the delamination region are anisotropic and the delamination itself occurs in the resin layer between the plies. Thus the crack is in an anisotropic, inhomogeneous medium where the interpretation of stress fields is rather problematic. More pragmatically the test specimens are usually in the form of slender beams from which G may be calculated directly so there is little incentive to consider K .

There are more profound arguments for preferring G which have stemmed mostly from the UK where the inheritors of the Griffith tradition have used energy with great success in widely different systems such as rubbers [1], polymers [2] and other materials. Such work takes the view that G_c is a real material property and is the correct way of characterising toughness. Whatever the motivation delamination is routinely characterised using G_c values and the data have become important in comparing materials with the attendant commercial implications. The values are also used in design schemes for structures and so have considerable importance. This has resulted in a substantial activity in developing standard testing protocols and in particular in the USA via ASTM, in Europe via the European Structural Integrity Society (ESIS) and in Japan via the Japanese Industrial Standards Group (JIS). The majority of the effort has been on a mode I protocol and there is now an ASTM standard available (ASTM D5528) [3], an ESIS protocol and a Japanese standard (JIS K7086). There are also versions of mode II and mixed-mode protocols being developed in all three groups

With all this going on it was apparent that there was potentially a great benefit in having an agreed common standard. To this end there have been several meetings of the three groups with a good degree of agreement and beneficial interaction. However, there are significant differences between the three mode I protocols in spite of these efforts. This paper will seek to highlight these and to seek their cause.

2. STANDARDS DEVELOPMENT

Many would view the generation of standard test methods as a low level intellectual activity. It is seen as mundane in that one simply explores details until one eventually eliminates variability by a process of attrition. This is not the case since it is extremely difficult, and vitally important, to establish the philosophy of the standard at the outset. What is the test for and what are one's expectations of the results it produces? A standard test is inevitably a compromise between the measurement of some absolute material property under rigorously defined conditions and what it is sensible to expect from users of the standard given limited time and resources as well as differences in operator experience. Some illustrations of this will now be given.

2.1 FRACTURE INITIATION

If one defines fracture toughness one must define the conditions under which the fracture occurs. G values used for the R curve are energy per unit area and generally come from energy difference computations of the experimental data. Fracture mechanics always assumes a pre-existing crack and then describes its behaviour. Initiation here is thus the condition when an existing crack starts to grow. In some tests, initiation coincides with instability, ie the specimen goes bang, so there is no difficulty, in principle, in defining the condition. In most cases, however, even when there is instability some stable growth occurs prior to instability. In a mode I delamination double cantilever beam (DCB) test crack growth is mostly stable and the initial linear loading line becomes curved as the stiffness decreases with crack growth. As the growth continues this gives a falling load curve so there is a maximum in load but it usually occurs after initiation. This is shown diagrammatically in fig 1. In principle, therefore, one could watch the crack tip and then record when it first moved and this would coincide with the onset of non-linearity on the diagram. In practice these two points rarely coincide [4]. Deciding whether a stationary crack has started to move is a difficult judgement and operator dependent. Similarly defining a deviation from linearity is scale dependent and there is also the problem that non-linearity can result from processes other than crack growth such as damage or large displacements. In addition, initiation has been shown to occur at the centre of the specimen first [5] in some circumstances which further complicates matters. This has been recognised in standards for other materials and a scheme used where a line is drawn for a 5% compliance increase (or stiffness decrease) as shown in in fig 1. If this intersects the line the intersection point is used as initiation. If the maximum load occurs before the intersection then that value is taken. This definition is, of course, arbitrary and is almost certainly post initiation but it is repeatable. In effect it recognises the uncertainties and says that we must allow a substantial amount of growth in order to be reasonably certain that it is crack initiation and also that one can detect it repeatable but we are sacrificing the definition of "true" initiation [Note that a 5% increase in compliance here is equivalent to a 1.5% increase in crack length, ie < 1 mm for the commonly used 50 mm precrack].

These compromises become important if one adopts the lower bound philosophy in Fracture Mechanics. This is the basis of most standards which are designed to give crack initiation values under the most stringent conditions, ie the highest possible constraint at the crack tip as in plane strain. In metals and polymers standards the 5% offset method is used together with plane strain conditions to give minimum values [6,7,8]. In composites there are no size criteria for plane strain but the inter-laminar layer is heavily constrained to give a minimum value and ASTM has favoured the visual definition to ensure this minimum is measured. The compromise in the standard is that all four values are measured and one is free to choose. There is no definitive evidence for which is the best value but none is the "true" initiative value if indeed such a thing exists since there is some evidence that the closer one looks the lower the visual value you will record [4]. However small a load one applies to a crack it will induce some

change at the crack tip but is it initiation?

Figure 1. Initiation Determination

2.2 CRACK SHARPNESS

The previous discussion omitted any mention of the nature of the crack which is initiated. To be consistent with the minimum value philosophy one should start with the sharpest possible crack and in metals [6] and polymers [7,8], this is achieved by pre cracking via either fatigue for metals or using a razor blade for polymers. In both cases one seeks a "natural" sharp crack and then initiates fracture from it. For composite laminates the initial crack is made by inserting a non-adhering metal foil or plastic film in the laminate during manufacture. In the ASTM standard a plastic film of thickness no greater than 13 microns is specified and the test is conducted by initiating fracture from this defect. There are many practical problems associated with this method including partial adherence of the film, resin rich zones and film folding at the crack tip as well as the question of how thin should the film be. The value used is the thinnest practically possible but at 13 microns there are difficulties with wrinkling and splitting of the film. With well made samples the results are quite consistent but experience in round-robin tests has shown many cases of erratic values arising from adhered or blunt defects.

All this could be overcome and the method made more consistent with other standards by precracking. If the molded-in defect is loaded until it grows a small amount or is razor notched, then more consistent results are obtained and this has been demonstrated in ESIS tests. ASTM has resisted the inclusion of precracking because it believes that the possibility of crack bridging could give falsely high values of initiation toughness. We will return to the issues of bridging in the next section but here it is only necessary to note that if G_c is crack length dependent, for whatever reasons, then precracking moves the crack up the R curve and again one does not have a minimum value. Precracking in mode II or using razor blades can avoid bridging, but there is no large body of evidence to support any particular scheme. ESIS experience has been that much more consistent results within a laboratory are obtained when precracking is used though inter laboratory variations persist.

2.3 THE R CURVE

R or resistance curves occur in many materials and there are standards for their determination in metals [9]. They are also encountered in polymers [10] and for tough materials they are very useful for comparing the performance of materials [11]. The rising toughness in these cases stems from the development of plastic deformation as the crack grows and in general they are not geometry independent. It turns out that if sizes encountered in practice are used there is no strong size dependence and hence the relationship to performance in components can be established [11].

In composites, R curves are usually attributed to fibre bridging although multiple cracking or extensive matrix ductility may also contribute. In the standard tests uniaxial lay ups are used and in some cases the crack growth results in fibres bridging the crack faces as shown in fig 2.

The amount increases until it reaches a limit value so the R curve tends to a plateau as shown. Fibre bridging is much more prevalent in poorly bonded systems and in misaligned fibres and is a much stronger effect in cross ply systems. It is also quite strongly geometry dependent since large displacements tend to break the bridges so thin specimens have less bridging than thick ones. With this in mind the minimum values school argues that any results involving bridges should be disregarded since its occurrence is variable and not guaranteed. The preclusion of precracking also stems from these arguments. The net result of the minimum values philosophy is the determination of a single toughness value at initiation from a molded-in defect.

Figure 2. The 'R' Curve and Fibre Bridging

Pursuers of the 'R' curve method would alternatively argue that the curve contained useful information even though it is neither unique nor a minimum. If the actual thickness of laminates is used in the test then the occurrence of bridging does give an indication of how the material will perform in practice and that is of value, particularly in comparative studies. The 'R' curve philosophy recognises the initiation definition problem and allows some arbitrary but reliably reproducible values to be used. The ASTM and ESIS standards both allow the 'R' curve to be determined but they differ in that ASTM does not allow precracking. It is the ESIS view that some limited amount should be prescribed in order to overcome the insert problems which far outweighs any bridging effects. The current ESIS protocol advocates determining initiation from both an insert and a precrack and using the lower value which does address the issue of possible bridging. In fact bridging is not particularly common in well made composites and should not be an overriding consideration in determining methodology.

2.4 MODE II TESTING

No widely accepted standard exists for a Mode II test yet, although a JIS, ENF standard (K7086, March 1993) is available in Japanese, and it is under active investigation by all three groups. Many of the issues discussed for Mode I occur here and the question of the insert and precracking is essentially the same. Bridging does not seem to occur in Mode II but 'R' curves do [12]. ASTM currently favours the use of the end notch flexure (ENF) test in which a commonly available three point bend test rig may be used. Unfortunately the ENF test is unstable so no 'R' curves can be measured. There are also significant non-linearities arising from the geometry which result in curvature similar to that arising from crack growth thus rendering the non-linearity method difficult. It is also hard to see the crack tip in Mode II since there is no crack opening so that visual technique is even more problematic than in Mode I.

The end loaded split (ELS) test is favoured by ESIS since it does give stable crack growth so an 'R' curve can be measured. It has somewhat better geometric characteristics but the visual detection problems remain. The difficulty here is marking initiation values on an 'R' curve and not in deciding single numbers. Both methods have problems in the analysis compared with the DCB test. These arise because uncracked specimens have a substantial compliance in these configurations while for the DCB it is zero for zero crack length. Thus crack growth leads to a

relatively smaller compliance (C) change with crack growth and attendant problems in defining dC/da . Currently these are unresolved differences between curve fitting and beam theory methods. It would appear that the necessary degree of accuracy required in determining C is very difficult to achieve. Similar observations pertain in the various forms of mixed-mode tests.

3. CONCLUSIONS

Difficulties in defining and detecting crack initiation preclude any rigorous definition though indirect methods may help in the future [7]. Some compromise is necessary and ESIS experience would suggest that the 5% offset or maximum load value is preferable to visual or non-linearity methods. Initial defects which are molded in are prone to problems and some form of precracking is necessary. A compromise where both are included is a possibility. The uncertainties surrounding 'R' curves are outweighed by the insights obtained into the toughness of the material and they form a useful basis for material comparison. A similar set of considerations apply in Mode II plus some additional problems in analysis but an 'R' curve based approach seems likely to be the most useful.

REFERENCES

1. R.F. Breidenbach and G.J. Lake, Application of fracture mechanics to rubber articles, including tyres', *Phil. Trans. R.Soc. London A299*, 189-202 (1981).
2. J.G. Williams, 'Fracture Mechanics of Polymers', Ellis Horwood, Chichester, 1985.
3. ASTM D5528-94a Standard Test Method for Mode I Inter-laminar Fracture Toughness of Unidirectional Fibre-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites.
4. P. Flüeler and A.J. Brunner, 'Crack Propagation in Fibre Reinforced Composite Materials Analysed with in-situ Microfocal x-ray Radiography and Simultaneous Acoustic Emission', *Proceedings ECCM-CTS (Amsterdam)*, 385-394 (1992).
5. T. de Kalbemann, R. Jaggi, P. Flüeler, H.H. Kausch and P. Davies, *J. Mat. Sci, Letters* 11, 543-6, (1992).
6. ASTM E399 Test Method of Plane-Strain Fracture Toughness of Metallic Materials
7. ASTM D5045-91a, Plane-Strain Fracture Toughness and Strain Energy Release Rate of Plastic Materials.
8. European Structural Integrity Society (ESIS), A Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) Standard for Determining K_{IC} and G_C for Plastics. (March 1990).
9. ASTM E1152-87, Standard test method for determining J-R curves.
10. ESIS, A Testing Protocol for Conducting J-Crack Growth Resistance Curve Tests on Plastics, (May 1994).
11. D.D. Huang, *Proceedings ANTEC*, Boston, (1995).
12. S. Hashemi, A.J. Kinloch and J.G. Williams, 'The analysis of inter laminar fracture in uniaxial fibre-polymer composites'. *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. A427*, 173-199, (1990).

